

IMAGE COMPRESSION ON PLÉIADES NEO

Christophe LE LANN⁽¹⁾, Guillaume ROZIER⁽²⁾

⁽¹⁾*Airbus Defence and Space SAS
1 bd Jean Moulin, 78990 Élancourt, France
Email: christophe.lelann@airbus.com*

⁽²⁾*Airbus Defence and Space SAS
1 bd Jean Moulin, 78990 Élancourt, France
Email: guillaume.rozier@airbus.com*

ABSTRACT

Pléiades Neo is an Earth observation mission composed of 4 satellites, developed, launched and operated by Airbus Defence and Space, with a first launch in 2021.

The CORECI2 unit, designed and manufactured by Airbus Defence and Space at Élancourt, is the core component between optical instruments and downlink channels, offering CCompression, REcording and CIPHERING features, with unprecedented performances.

The compression part implements an altered version of the CCSDS 122.0-B-2 standard. Some of them started in 2015 with the OTOS project, in the frame of a CNES study, which analyzed different possibilities of standard modifications and compression architectures.

Airbus further optimized the compression core algorithm and architecture in the frame of the CORECI2 unit development, started in 2016. Indeed, the algorithm has been deeply optimized for efficient implementation on a Microchip RTG4 FPGA, achieving high performances with a much lower footprint than the traditional CCSDS 122.0-B-2 implementation, without altering image quality.

The compression core is integrated as part of a complete SoC infrastructure, implemented in pure RTL. The synthesized results on RTG4 show that this implementation meets mission expectations.

Keywords

Compression, OTOS, CORECI2

THE NEED FOR A NEW CONSTELLATION

Earth observation satellites instrument resolution, agility and swath are continuously improving, in response to customer ever increasing demands. Airbus Defence and Space launched in 2021 its new Earth observation constellation, named Pléiades Neo. It features 30cm resolution at 14km swath with high agility and high tasking reactivity.

This new generation required a technological upgrade of the on-board image compression unit technology, to cope with the increased input data rate. The CORECI2 has been designed as a combined solution offering image compression, recording (file storage) and ciphering in one unit.

It implements a modified version of the CCSDS 122.0-B-2 algorithm, maximizing image quality for a given compression rate while enabling an efficient FPGA implementation into a Microchip RTG4 radiation-hardened FPGA.

ALGORITHM MODIFICATIONS FROM THE CCSDS 122.0-B-2 STANDARD

Fixed-Rate Compression Algorithms

The MRCPB Algorithm

Before the publication of the CCSDS 122.0 standard, Airbus Defence and Space developed in 2001 its own compression algorithm called MRCPB (“Multi-Résolution par Codage de Plans Binaires”, French for “Multi-Resolution

by Bit Plane Encoding”). As it was partly inspired by the JPEG2000 standard, it used either a same 9/7 Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) – which is the one the CCSDS 122.0 standard also selected – or the 5/3 DWT. The output coefficients were encoded using a specific Bit Plane Encoder, different from the CCSDS 122.0 standard, with fixed rate output.

This algorithm was implemented into the WICOM ASIC (Atmel 350nm radiation-hardened technology), used in the successful CORECI series of units (Pléiades constellation, Spot 6, Spot 7, etc) as well as mission-specific units (Solar Orbiter, Sentinel 2, etc). Each ASIC processed up to 20 Mpix/s of 13 bits, as presented in [1].

The CCSDS 122.0-B-2 algorithm

Later on, the CCSDS 122.0 standard was published. Airbus implemented this algorithm in the CWICOM ASIC (CCSDS Wavelet Image COMpression), in the frame of an ESA contract. This ASIC is still available through ESA distribution.

This ASIC consumes 1Mgates plus 5Mb internal RAM memory in the Atmel ATC18RHA radiation-hardened technology, but requires no external memory (notably no SDRAM). It supports both lossy and lossless flavors at 60Mpix/s 16b, as already presented in [2] and [3].

Algorithm performance (image quality for a given compression rate) is similar to that of the MRCPB algorithm.

Limitations

In both algorithms, output bitstream is truncated to the target bitrate, resulting in a fixed-rate compression. This situation is not optimal:

- On image regions of low entropy, noise gets compressed and transmitted, resulting in useless consumption of mass memory and downlink bandwidth.
- On image regions of high entropy (eg. urban areas), useful information is lost.

Thus, the Signal-to-Noise Ratio is not constant across the whole image acquisition.

Neither MRCPB nor standard algorithms (CCSDS 122.0-B-2, JPEG2000, JPEG-LS) offer localized control over image quality.

Toward Local Quality Control Algorithms

To cope with this limitation, multiple R&D actions were started internally at Airbus Defence and Space and conjointly with the CNES.

The MRCPA Algorithm

The MCRPA algorithm (“Multi-Résolution à Codage par Plans Adaptés à l’instrument”, French for “Multi-Resolution by Plane Encoding Adapted to the instrument”) was a first evolution. It involved noise normalization before compression through an Anscombe transform, denoising steps, and a specific variable-rate encoder. Parameters enabled selecting the compression noise level with respect to instrument noise.

The CNES-Airbus OTOS Study

In the frame of the CNES OTOS program (“Observation de la Terre Optique Super-résolue”, French for “Super-resolved Optical Earth Observation”), Airbus Defence and Space also implemented algorithm evolutions resulting from CNES studies.

It involved noise level evaluation at the scale of an 8x8 pixels block, for image quality control at block level. A new Bit Plane Encoder was also defined.

Further Airbus Improvements

Both algorithms showed improvements from the CCSDS 122.0-B-2 standard, achieving better overall image quality at equivalent compression rate (at image scale), or conversely, achieving a better compression rate at equivalent image quality.

However, the Bit Plane Encoder used a significant part of available FPGA resources, making it unsuitable for implementation in a RTG4 as part of a complex system.

From that situation, Airbus Defence and Space developed a new encoder, named GOLRA (GOLomb Run Amp), using Golomb coding and Run Length coding, of much lower hardware complexity (4 times smaller). The efficiency of GOLRA is similar and often slightly better (up to -2%) than CCSDS 122.0-B-2 Bit Plane Encoder.

DC components are located first within the output bitstream. This enables very fast thumbnail generation (« quicklook »), on ground upon downlink, for real-time display of downlinked images.

Final CORECI2 Algorithm

Fig. 1. Final CORECI2 Algorithm

CORECI2 compression algorithm controls the local image quality everywhere in the image at a small scale as needed for close visual analysis. The image quality is user controlled for each image acquisition. It allows control of the compression noise, from negligible with respect to instrument noise to above instrument noise in any local area of the image. The quantization with local image quality control is the result of the CNES OTOS study.

The general benefit is that the risk of visual compression artefact is under control. An estimated benefit is about 25% reduction of average bit rate for similar image quality. The required absolute compressed bit rate is highly dependent on instrument quality and ground resolution (image correlation).

CORECI2 compression produces a variable compressed data rate during image compression depending on local image complexity.

Each spectral band is compressed independently of the others.

THE CORECI2 UNIT

Fig. 2. The CORECI2 Unit

Fig. 3. Simplified Equipment Architecture

Acquisition

The Pléiades Neo constellation uses a new instrument called NAOMIX, which is a push-broom type sensor offering a 30cm ground sampling distance over a 14km swath, with both panchromatic and 6 spectral bands. The output sampling ADCs thus generate 1.54 Gpix/s of 14 bits each, for a total of roughly 21.1 Gbps toward the CORECI2 unit.

By design, the CORECI2 unit can acquire up to 2 Gpix/s (28 Gbps) input. These pixel lines are timestamped upon acquisition, with an accuracy down to a few ns (representing a positioning accuracy of a few mm at ground level), allowing for accurate begin and end of image acquisition, thus reducing the need for acquisition margins around the area of interest. For small images (typically common acquisition types include small square areas), this may be as efficient as a finding a better compression algorithm.

Pre-Processing

Upon reception by the CORECI2 unit, the input stream of pixels received from the NAOMIX instrument first goes through pre-processing before it can be compressed. These pre-processings mainly aim at reversing the NAOMIX instrument transfer function.

Fig. 4. Acquisition Chain Before Compression

Bimodal Effect Compensation

A bimodal effect compensation function is applied first, in order to correct the non-uniform response of the different NAOMIX ADCs sampling the line-CCD output signals.

Indeed, these ADCs are internally composed of multiple parallel acquisition chains, interleaved pixel-by-pixel, in a way to increase the sampling rate. There is no deterministic phasing of the acquisition chains interleaving with respect to the beginning of a line, so this compensation cannot be merged with the traditional CCD Non-Uniformity Correction.

CCD Non-Uniformity Correction

In order to correct the non-uniform response of the line-CCD device, a Non-Uniformity Correction (NUC) is further applied before the compression process.

There is one specific set of NUC parameters for each column of the image, so every pixel of a column is corrected with the same set of parameters.

Rounding

Pixels acquired on 14 bits are rounded down to 12 bits before compression.

Compression

The compression core implements the previously described algorithm, with a high efficiency so as to process 2 pixels per clock cycle (thus up to 180 Mpix/s per compression core) while maintaining a low footprint.

Achieving this performance required careful adaptation of each datapath stage to the RTG4 FPGA low-level specificities: LUT topology, LUT/FF ratio, DSP datapath capabilities, RAM geometry, DSP and RAM density, routability, etc.

Compression parameters (quality target, noise parameters, etc) and NUC coefficients can be selected independently for each image acquisition.

This compression core includes a final encapsulation stage, converting the compressed bitstream into CCSDS 133.0-B-2 space packets. The secondary header notably includes the acquisition timestamp related to the compressed lines.

A bypass mode is also available, for space packet encapsulation in raster scan mode (without compression).

Final resource usage is 33k Look-Up Tables (LUT) and 29k Flip-Flops (FF), hence approximately 22% of a RTG4.

Recording

Compressed images are stored into a non-volatile memory, enabling for flexible satellite operations: acquisition and downlink are two independent operations that may happen simultaneously or separately.

A NAND flash controller offers 12 Tb of radiation-hardened memory capacity, with proper bad block management and SEE management, as detailed in [4].

Indeed, COTS NAND flash had to be qualified for space operation through a test campaign executed directly by Airbus Defence and Space, leading to the characterization of this component behavior within a space environment, failure modes and recovery procedures. A new “datasheet” could then be derived for the COTS component, and a dedicated flash controller be designed with proper mitigation. The resulting controller meets the expectations of less than 10^{-12} errors/bit.

A flash-aware specific file system was designed for memory area organization into files.

Ciphering

Compressed images can be further downlinked using either a 2-channels X-band transmitter toward ground stations at 1.2 Gbps, or a laser communication terminal toward the European Data Relay System (EDSR) at 1.8 Gbps, or both simultaneously.

This implies formatting compressed images into Transfer Frames and Channel Access Data Unit (CADU), and notably ciphering Frames content using ciphering algorithm, running at more than 3 Gbps.

Multiple ciphering keys are available, allowing for multiple independent ground stations, including ground stations directly owned and operated by end customers.

System-on-a-Chip Infrastructure

These multiple datapath elements are integrated as part of a complex System-on-a-Chip (SoC) infrastructure in pure-RTL.

Fig. 5. Simplified FPGA Architecture

A softcore processor is used for high level management, TM/TC communication with the OBC, file system operations, as well as low-level sequencing.

A DDR2 controller offers more than 20 Gbps of SEE-protected volatile memory bandwidth for all datapath elements to use, through a common bus interconnect, internally to a board's FPGA.

This internal communication network is further extended by a high-speed and reliable Spacefibre interconnection network between the multiple boards constituting the CORECI2 unit, through multi-Gbps SERDES links.

Outcome

Overall CORECI2 design fills 79% of a Microchip RTG4 FPGA. These resources span over 57 clock domains, which seems a large value, but is directly related to the high number of external interfaces requiring dedicated reception clocks: DDR2 memories (one clock per die), NAND flash memories, and SERDES links (one clock per lane). Most of the logic is clocked at 90 MHz or 180 MHz.

This combination of high filling rate and high frequency required strong expertise in FPGA design, and led to the discovery of issues with the RTG4 silicon itself and with its Libero software suite, leading to Warning Notices publication and new Libero releases. Those difficulties were overcome thanks to a strong support from Microchip.

The first two Pléiades Neo satellites were launched in 2021. A second batch of two satellites are scheduled to be launched end 2022. This 4 satellites constellation enables two revisits per day, and a total of 2 million square km acquired every day.

Fig. 6. Extract of a Pléiades Neo Sample Image

CONCLUSION AND ON-GOING DEVELOPMENTS

The CORECI2 unit has been developed from 2017 to 2019, and meets Pléiades Neo mission's specification.

The lossy CORECI2 compression algorithm provides a better image quality at similar compression ratio than the CCSDS 122.0-B-2 algorithm.

The CORECI2 compression core has already been reused for another Earth Observation program, using another FPGA technology.

The CORECI2 equipment architecture is scalable to easily adjust performances to the mission needs. Being FPGA-based instead of ASIC-based, the architecture brings high flexibility to adapt to other missions (different instrument, different compression algorithm – including hyper-spectral or radar –, etc). This architecture has already been adapted for use in ESA Copernicus CO2M PDHU unit, and Mars Sample Return (MSR-ERO) missions.

Airbus Defence and Space is already working on its next generation mass memory and image compression unit.

Next generation of Mass Memories and Image Processing units are targeting European technologies, with the use of NanoXplore NGULTRA FPGA component, which happens to already embed a complete SoC infrastructure as a hard-IP (without consuming FPGA resources). Airbus Defence and Space was involved in the design of this SoC through the

DAHLIA consortium. This FPGA will be coupled to DDR4 memories, increasing the available bandwidth for datapath elements such as the compression core.

Being a new FPGA technology, the compression core will have to be reworked to be tightly optimized for the target technology properties, much like the CORECI2 compression core was optimized for the Microchip RTG4 technology.

It will bring a new performance gap for the next generation of observation satellites, with 100's of Gbps of image acquisition through optical fibers, and 100's of Tb of non-volatile memory for file system storage.

This unit will embed an Artificial Intelligence (AI) system. It will notably enable on-board data analysis.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Wagner, JL. Poupat, "Image Compression Mass Memory and Ciphering in one box", *OBPDC 2014, On-Board Payload Data Processing Conference*, proceedings of the conference held in 2014.
- [2] JL. Poupat, "CWICOM & CORECI: Towards a Highly Integrated & Innovative Image Compression Unit", *DASIA 2011, DAta Systems In Aerospace*, proceedings of the conference held 17-20 May, 2011.
- [3] JL. Poupat, "CWICOM: A Highly Integrated & Innovative CCSDS Image Compression ASIC", *DASIA 2013, Data Systems In Aerospace*, proceedings of the conference held 14-16 May, 2013.
- [4] C. Le Lann, "Mass Memory: Status and Perspectives", *DASIA 2022, Data Systems In Aerospace, proceedings of the conference held 17-19 May, 2022*.